

HUMAN–ROBOT WITH NLP

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

We are working on Human–Robot with user-friendly designed and manufactured to serve a multi purpose work, pushing beyond the boundaries and limitation of service robots. The embedded visual engine allows for the real-time object detection, and facial recognition, Real-time emotional detection, with video content analysis and summarization with natural language processing capability facilitates an efficient communication with the user. This Human–Robot is built a base on NLP engine to understand the response the user speech and execute the instruction as per need. Also, Human-Robot has advanced 360 mapping and localisation sensor to achieve autonomous patrolling.

2. Aim and Target

We have the aim to provide service in different sectors such as Healthcare, Education, Entertainment, surveillance, Airlines and hospitality industries, etc.

3. Keywords

Human–Robot, NLP , Real-time object detection, Facial recognition, Real-time emotional detection, video content analysis and summarisation

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